

Analysis of the Vegetation Monitoring Research from the Aspect of Anthropogenic and Climate Influences by Remote Sensing Methods

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Abstract: Monitoring of vegetation vigour appears as key element in studying environmental dynamics. Changes in vegetation are directly related to certain climate drivers as well as human activities, and there is an important need to understand their mutual relationship. This review analyses the development of remote sensing methods considering the changes that can be monitored with the help of certain vegetation indices. The emphasis is on the examination of indices such as NDVI, EVI, LAI, SAVI, AVRI as one of the most effective methodologies to identify variations in the vegetation based on remote sensing imagery. The shift from simple trend detection to complex causal inference models that utilize multi-source data was evaluated. Thereby, enabling the attribution of these changes to either climate-driven or human induced to better understand their complex interactions.

Keywords: vegetation index; climate change, anthropogenic effects; trend analysis; remote sensing.

1 Introduction

Remote sensing methods used to monitor vegetation are becoming increasingly important for a better understanding of ecosystem dynamics, climate interactions and anthropogenic impact on the environment (Xu et al. 2024). Since the introduction of the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) in the 1970s, remote sensing has evolved to include diverse vegetation indices and advanced analytical techniques, and particularly in vegetation assessment over large areas, enabling long temporal assessments (de Beurs et al. 2009). The practical importance of this issue is in its applications for environmental protection, land management, and climate change reduction, with studies reporting that over 80% of global vegetation areas shows significant trends linked to environmental and human factors (Guo et al 2018).

Despite extensive research, challenges remain in differentiating natural climatic influences from anthropogenic effects on vegetation dynamics (Xu et al. 2018, 2024). Existing studies often focus on single vegetation index or limited spatio-temporal scales, leading to inconsistent interpretations of vegetation changes (Wang et al. 2023). Moreover, controversies persist regarding the relative contributions of climate versus human activities, with some findings emphasizing climatic drivers in greening trends (Yu et al. 2024), while others highlight human-induced degradation (de Beurs et al. 2009, Xu et al. 2018, 2024).

The general idea of this review focus on the integration of vegetation indices — such as Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI), Leaf Area Index (LAI), Green Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (GDNVI), Kernel Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (kNDVI), Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index (SAVI), Modified Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index (MSAVI and MSAVI2), and Atmospherically Resistant Vegetation Index (ARVI) —with statistical and spatial analysis methods, including Partial Correlation Analysis, Trend Detection, Residual Trend Analysis (RESTREND), Linear Regression Analysis, and Mann-Kendall Trend Analysis. These tools collectively enable the quantification of vegetation status, the attribution of changes to climatic or anthropogenic factors, and the identification of ecologically sensitive zones. Establishing these relationships is essential for advancing vegetation monitoring and informing restoration strategies.

2 Materials and methods

Due to the need to approach the analysis in the right way, it was necessary to break down all the key factors. The first factor was vegetation monitoring, and by insight into the Scopus scientific database, vegetation monitoring with the help of remote sensing methods is most efficiently done with the help of vegetation indices. It was also observed there that there are different types of vegetation indices that are designed to better detect vegetation with regard to the configuration of the terrain, areas with a high amount of moisture, urban areas, areas with a pronounced canopy, bare land areas, etc. Climate drivers are also usually considering as primary triggers of vegetation increase or decrease.

It was also observed through the analysis of the scientific database that with regard to the development of remote sensing methods and the appearance of more precise ones, the use of these images for the purposes of vegetation analysis is occurring. This includes Landsat, Sentinel, Modis, GIMMS datasets. With an insight into vegetation monitoring and the availability of images, it was finally necessary to find a correlation between anthropogenic impact and vegetation. Partial Correlation Analysis”, “Theil-Sen Median Trend Analysis”, “Residual Trend Analysis”, “Linear Regression Analysis” and “Mann-Kendall Trend Analysis” was used to quantify impact of anthropogenic effects on vegetation.

Scopus database was analysed to establish the connection between NDVI and specific analysis. Search conditions

were entered in two lines connected by the Boolean operator AND, where the first line contains the keyword “NDVI” and the second line contains the keywords “Partial Correlation Analysis”, “Theil-Sen Median Trend Analysis”, “Residual Trend Analysis”, “Linear Regression Analysis” and “Mann-Kendall Trend Analysis”.

3 Results

3.1 Vegetation indices

Vegetation indices (VI) exploit the characteristic spectral reflectance properties of vegetation across the electromagnetic spectrum. Healthy vegetation exhibits low reflectance in the visible red region (approximately 650 nm) due to chlorophyll absorption, high reflectance in the near-infrared region (800-900 nm) due to leaf internal structure, and moderate reflectance in the green region (550 nm) (Giovos et al. 2021). These spectral properties form the basis for most vegetation indices.

The development of vegetation indices has progressed through several generations, each addressing specific limitations of earlier indices. First-generation indices like NDVI provided simple, robust measures of vegetation greenness but suffered from saturation at high biomass levels and sensitivity to soil background and atmospheric effects (Xue and Su 2017). Second-generation indices such as EVI and SAVI incorporated corrections for these confounding factors (Giovos et al. 2021). More recent developments include kernel-based approaches (KNDVI) that address non-linear relationships between spectral reflectance and vegetation properties.

Vegetation indices serve multiple purposes in agricultural and environmental applications. They are used to estimate biophysical parameters, including leaf area index, biomass, chlorophyll content, and water status. They enable monitoring of crop growth stages, detection of stress conditions, assessment of spatial variability within fields, and forecasting of crop yields (Giovos et al. 2021, Kokhan and Vostokov 2020). Comparative analysis of selected vegetation indices, along with its mathematical formulations paired with corresponding advantages and limitations is presented in Table 1.

3.2 Methodological approaches for climate change and anthropogenic effects differentiation in vegetation monitoring

A number of methods play distinct roles in trend detection and are widely used together in vegetation studies to separate climate and human effects. Partial correlation isolates the statistical association between vegetation (e.g., NDVI) and one climate variable while holding other climate variables constant, it is applied to map where vegetation responds to specific climatic drivers (Li et al. 2019). Studies shows that precipitation, temperature, solar radiation and evapotranspiration have a specific impact depending on the tested areas, especially for the areas with difference in humidity, elevation and proximity to populated areas. Theil-Sen median trend is used as a nonparametric trend estimator for long-term time series and is commonly paired with a significance test to report trend magnitudes across pixels or regions (Xu et al. 2022). Residual trend analysis typically fits a regression (NDVI

Table 1. Comparative analysis of common VI used in vegetation monitoring.

VI Equation	Advantages	Limitations
$NDVI = \frac{NIR - RED}{NIR + RED}$	Simplicity Robustness Wide applicability	Saturation Soil background sensitivity Atmospheric effects
$EVI = 2.5x \frac{NIR - RED}{(NIR + 6xRED - 7.5xBLUE + 1)}$	Reduced saturation Atmospheric correction Soil background adjustment	Complexity Data requirements Computational intensity
$LAI = (3.618xEVI - 0.118)$	Physical meaning Universal parameter Model integration	Indirect measurement Saturation in indices Crop-specific relationships
$GNDVI = \frac{NIR - GREEN}{NIR + GREEN}$	Chlorophyll sensitivity Reduced saturation Canopy penetration	Soil sensitivity Atmospheric effects Limited season sensitivity
$kNDVI = \tanh(NDVI^2)$	Reduced saturation Improved linearity Enhanced accuracy	Computational complexity Limited adoption Calibration requirements
$SAVI = \frac{(NIR - RED)}{(NIR + RED)} x(1 + L)$	Soil correction Early season performance Improved accuracy	Parameter selection Complexity Dense vegetation
$MSAVI = \frac{2xNIR + 1 - \sqrt{(2xNIR + 1)^2 - 8x(NIR - RED)}}{2}$	Automatic adjustment Consistent performance Soil correction	Computational complexity Interpretation Saturation
$AVRI = \frac{NIR - RB}{NIR + RB}$	Atmospheric resistance Temporal consistency	Limited documentation Validation needs

Table 2. Comparison of methods used for quantifying human and climate induced vegetation changes.

Method	Advantages	Limitations
Partial correlation	Controls for confounding climate variables to indicate where a specific climate factor (e.g., temperature or precipitation) is associated with vegetation changes	Does not quantify human effects and can only identify conditional associations rather than causal attribution.
Theil–Sen median trend	Robust trend detection across noisy satellite NDVI datasets and widespread in large-scale vegetation mapping studies	No attribution—they indicate where and how strongly vegetation changes, but not why.
Residual trend analysis	Directly targets human influence by attributing the portion of NDVI change unexplained by modeled climate to anthropogenic drivers, widely used to estimate percentage contributions of climate versus human activities	Assumes the climate model is correctly specified, unmodeled climate processes, omitted variables, or model misspecification can bias the inferred human contribution
Linear regression analysis	Simple and interpretable for both trend estimation and as the regression backbone of residual attribution approaches	Attribution sensitive to covariate choice and model form, simple linear fits may omit nonlinear or lagged climate–vegetation relationships.
Mann–Kendall trend	It can effectively process time series with gaps or missing values (e.g., due to cloud cover) without requiring data interpolation, which might introduce bias.	The standard MK test is poorly suited for data with periodic or seasonal cycles (e.g., natural spring green-up).

versus climate predictors) and interprets the trend in the model residuals as the signal of non-climatic (mainly anthropogenic) influence (Geng et al. 2023, Li et al. 2019). Regression coefficients can be calculated from the period with relatively little impact of human activities on vegetation changes and it is used for NDVI observed determination. Then NDVI predicted values for testing period can be calculated using regression coefficients from previous period. Residual between observed NDVI and predicted NDVI will present influence of the anthropogenic activities. Also, to validate the method correlation coefficient of observed NDVI and predicted NDVI can be tested on areas with no human influence. Linear regression analysis (ordinary least squares at pixel or regional scale) is used both for simple trend estimation and as the basis for regression-based attribution (Chen et al. 2025). Mann–Kendall trend test is a distribution-free test for monotonic trends and is routinely used to assess the statistical significance of the trends estimated by Theil–Sen or linear regression (Li et al. 2022, Xu et al. 2022). Each method contributes differently to differentiating anthropogenic influence and climate change effect, and common practice is to combine them into a workflow to offset individual limitations, this can be seen in Table 2.

3.3 Scopus database analysis and the correlation between the NDVI and anthropogenic analytical methodologies

To establish the relationship between NDVI and specific type of analysis Scopus database search was performed. The process was induced by focusing on key words “NDVI” as key vegetation index on one side and key methodological approaches on the other side: “Partial Correlation Analysis”, “Theil-Sen Median Trend Analysis”, “Residual Trend Analysis”, “Linear Regression Analysis” and “Mann-Kendall Trend Analysis”. This approach resulted overall 467, 121, 345, 1963 and 655 documents

respectively (Figure 1). Furthermore, a significant increase in yearly published articles on this subject can be seen from 2015 onwards.

4 Discussion

NDVI is easy to calculate and interpret, requiring only two spectral bands and effective across diverse vegetation types and ecosystems. To maintain sensitivity at higher biomass levels than NDVI, EVI may be used. Evaluation of the canopy structure in high-biomass ecosystems can be done by introducing third band (blue band) with EVI. Also, LAI index can be used for comparison of different vegetation types. Furthermore, if assessments of crops in early growth stages or arid environments are being planned, the SAVI index has been shown to be more effective, additionally, improved correlation with crop yields is shown by SAVI compared to NDVI in areas with variable soil backgrounds.

Atmospherically Resistant Vegetation Index (AVRI) can be used for comparison of vegetation conditions across different dates with varying atmospheric conditions.

NDVI is widely used in scientific studies in correlation with Partial Correlation Analysis, Theil-Sen Median Trend Analysis Residual Trend Analysis, Linear Regression Analysis and Mann-Kendall Trend Analysis. We notice a growing trend, especially since 2015, which is obviously related to various sources of data sets that are increasingly publicly available and platforms for data processing and visualization.

On the other hand, when comparing methods of analysis that identify link between climate-vegetation and human contribution, each method has complementary strengths and limitations. All methods are computationally lightweight and are implemented in standard statistical libraries and remote-sensing solutions and they can be implemented at pixel scale across large domains and

sometimes in cloud environments such as Google Earth Engine.

Partial correlation identifies the relationship between changes in specific climate driver and the corresponding response in vegetation indices. It is generally used to determine what single climate driver (precipitation, temperature, solar radiation, evapotranspiration) has most significant effect on vegetation. However, this method does not directly quantify anthropogenic impact on vegetation. Residual analyses on other hand can provide direct impact of anthropogenic actions on vegetation by separating changes in VI caused by natural factors and human activities. Residual represents difference between observed VI and predicted NDVI. Man Kendall Trend test is usually combined with Theil-Sen Median Trend as MK test identify positive or negative change in vegetation and significance, and TS median trend can quantify the magnitude.

Scientists adopt simple, reproducible pipelines (trend detection → climate control analysis → residual attribution) and the literature provides many region-specific examples of comparative use.

We can detect trends with Theil–Sen and test significance with Mann–Kendall, assess climate–vegetation relationships with Partial Correlation, and run Regression Residual Analysis to estimate human contributions. This pattern appears across multiple regional and national studies.

5 Conclusions

Vegetation monitoring research using remote sensing techniques uses various vegetation indices for identification and tracking of vegetation changes that are mostly driven by climate drivers and anthropogenic effects. NDVI continues to be most frequently used index, especially when comparing to statistical analysis that differentiate human and climate change effect on vegetation dynamics. NDVI remains the most frequently used index, particularly in studies employing statistical methods to distinguish the impacts of human activities and climate change on vegetation dynamics. To measure the specific impacts of climate and human activities on vegetation, advanced statistical techniques are used to isolate and quantify their individual effects. Menn-Kendal

Figure 1. Number of yearly documents found on Scopus database that combined NDVI vegetation index with a) Partial Correlation Analysis, b) Theil-Sen Median Trend Analysis, c) Residual Trend Analysis, d) Linear Regression Analysis and e) Mann-Kendall Trend Analysis.

and Theil-Sen analysis are usually used to determine the change in vegetation (positive or negative), and its significance, while Residual Trend Analyses can quantify the impact of human activities on vegetation change. It is also very important that VI observed and VI predicted are tested in areas without human influence to verify the regression model. Partial correlation analysis can provide insight on which climate drivers have dominant influence on vegetation change.

Future research should prioritize standardized protocols, and integrative approaches that combine remote sensing within in situ observations to improve attribution of vegetation dynamics to human and climatic drivers. Thereby supporting more effective ecological conservation, land management, and climate change mitigation efforts.

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